

An On-Premise Deep-Learning Pipeline for Robust Machine-Readable-Zone Extraction from Real-World Identity-Document Images

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Abstract—Automated reading of the Machine-Readable Zone (MRZ) of identity documents is a central step in digital identity verification, but robust extraction from real-world smartphone images remains difficult because of blur, glare, perspective distortion, and partial occlusion. Production-grade solutions are typically commercial, closed-source, and operate as black boxes, which is undesirable for privacy-sensitive on-premise deployments. This paper presents and evaluates a fully on-premise pipeline that converts a complete document image into an MRZ transcription through four stages: MRZ detection, geometric rectification, line splitting, and MRZ-adapted optical character recognition (OCR). For detection, a lightweight literature-based HED-MRZ baseline, a U-Net, and two vision-foundation-model backbones (DINOv2-S and DINOv3-L) are compared as binary segmentation models. For recognition, generic PaddleOCR systems and a commercial OCR service are compared against an SVTRv2-based connectionist temporal classification (CTC) recognizer that is pretrained on synthetically generated MRZ lines and fine-tuned on real MRZ crops. Models are evaluated on the public MIDV-500, MIDV-2020, and MIDV-LAIT datasets and on a private target-domain dataset, with paired statistical testing. U-Net, DINOv2-S, and DINOv3-L clearly outperform the HED-MRZ baseline, and MRZ-specific OCR adaptation substantially improves recognition over generic OCR. On the private target domain the end-to-end pipeline reaches 96.4% full-MRZ accuracy with a character error rate of 0.07%. The results indicate that accurate on-premise MRZ extraction is feasible without relying on closed commercial OCR services.

Index Terms—Machine-Readable Zone, optical character recognition, identity documents, semantic segmentation, vision transformers, document image analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital identity verification has become a core component of many online business processes. In sectors such as telecommunications, banking, and insurance, providers are legally obliged to confirm the identity of remote customers, and the volume of verification requests makes manual checking impractical, error-prone, and slow. This creates a strong demand for automated, machine-learning-based verification.

This work was carried out as part of the first author’s master’s thesis at the University of Applied Sciences Technikum Wien, in collaboration with an industrial partner that provided the private dataset and computing hardware.

A common verification step is reading the MRZ of an identity document. The MRZ encodes personal data—including name, date of birth, and document number—in a fixed format defined by ICAO Doc 9303 [1], using the OCR-B font and one of the standard layouts TD1, TD2, and TD3. Because the format includes check digits, MRZ recognition is unforgiving: a single character error can invalidate the extracted record. On controlled scans this task is largely solved, but real-world smartphone images introduce blur, glare, perspective distortion, partial occlusion, and varying illumination, which substantially degrade recognition [2].

Several specialized vendors offer commercial identity-verification services [3, 4]. These systems are, however, expensive, closed-source, and operate as black boxes, which is problematic when full control over data handling, deployment, and model behaviour is required. This motivates transparent on-premise alternatives.

MRZ extraction is typically divided into MRZ detection and OCR. Recent work has improved detection considerably, whereas OCR remains the harder subproblem, especially under distortion and blur [2, 5]. Although academic and industrial systems already address end-to-end (E2E) MRZ processing, many are proprietary, not fully reproducible, or not designed for on-premise deployment. A remaining gap is therefore a reproducible on-premise pipeline that combines modern detection with MRZ-adapted OCR and evaluates the *complete* processing chain—from a full document image to the final transcription—under a unified protocol. Isolated OCR performance on pre-cropped lines does not fully represent practical identity-verification conditions, because detection, rectification, and line splitting can introduce their own errors.

This paper addresses the question of whether an on-premise E2E pipeline that combines MRZ detection, geometric rectification, line splitting, and MRZ OCR can achieve robust MRZ recognition on real-world document images. Robustness is assessed using full-MRZ accuracy, line accuracy, character error rate (CER), cross-dataset performance, and stability across repeated runs. The main contributions are:

- 1) A fully on-premise, four-stage MRZ pipeline that maps

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed end-to-end MRZ pipeline.

a complete document image to an MRZ transcription and is evaluated E2E under a single protocol.

- 2) A systematic comparison of detection backbones—a literature-based HED-MRZ baseline, a U-Net, and two vision-foundation models (DINOv2-S, DINOv3-L)—across public benchmarks and a private target domain, with paired statistical testing.
- 3) An MRZ-adapted SVTRv2 CTC recognizer trained with a staged synthetic-to-real transfer-learning strategy and benchmarked against generic open-source OCR and a commercial OCR service.
- 4) A quantification of the gap between isolated OCR on ground-truth line crops and full-pipeline recognition, including cases in which the E2E pipeline is more accurate than OCR on idealized crops.

II. METHODS

A. Pipeline Overview

The pipeline takes a full document image as input and produces the final MRZ transcription through four stages: (i) MRZ detection, (ii) MRZ-block extraction and geometric rectification, (iii) line splitting, and (iv) MRZ OCR (Fig. 1). The two learning-based stages are detection and OCR; block extraction and line splitting are rule-based. The same train/test configurations are used for the component-level and the E2E experiments, so the final evaluation measures the combined effect of all four stages.

B. MRZ Detection

Detection is formulated as binary segmentation: the model predicts a pixel-level mask of the MRZ region, which is thresholded and mapped back to the original resolution. Four models of increasing specialization and capacity are compared. *HED-MRZ* is a lightweight, literature-inspired baseline that combines convolutional processing with Fast Hough Transform layers [6]; because no implementation or checkpoint was available, it was re-implemented from the published description and is therefore treated as a literature-inspired baseline rather than an exact reproduction. *U-Net* (ResNet-50 backbone) is a strong classical segmentation reference. *DINOv2-S* [7] and *DINOv3-L* [8] are self-supervised Vision-Transformer foundation models used with a frozen backbone and a trained segmentation head. Parameter counts differ

markedly: about 65,000 (HED-MRZ), 71.8 M (U-Net), 23.4 M total with 1.36 M trainable (DINOv2-S), and 305.1 M total with 2.02 M trainable (DINOv3-L).

All models share a unified training protocol: AdamW with learning rate 3×10^{-4} , a OneCycle cosine schedule, 30 epochs, and a combined BCE–Dice loss with increased foreground weighting to address the strong MRZ/background class imbalance. A fixed random seed was used, and checkpoints were selected on the best validation Intersection-over-Union (IoU). To improve robustness to real-world acquisition conditions, training used an augmentation policy comprising random rotation, motion blur, brightness/contrast jitter, JPEG-compression artefacts, random perspective distortion, zoom-out, and stripe occlusion. Model-specific settings differed: HED-MRZ and U-Net used 384×384 grayscale inputs, whereas DINOv2-S and DINOv3-L used 518×518 and 512×512 RGB inputs, respectively.

C. MRZ-Block Extraction and Line Splitting

The predicted mask is reduced to a single MRZ candidate by selecting the largest connected component. An approximate quadrilateral is estimated; if four corners are found, a perspective transform produces an axis-aligned, deskewed crop. If this crop yields a complete MRZ with valid check digits, it is accepted; otherwise the pipeline falls back to a rotated bounding box and re-runs splitting and recognition, retaining the better of the two results.

The rectified block is split into lines using an ICAO-based heuristic. The expected layout is inferred from the block aspect ratio: blocks with width/height ≥ 7.5 are treated as two-line MRZs (TD2/TD3) and split equidistantly into two regions, while smaller ratios are treated as three-line MRZs (TD1). Each candidate line is validated with a binarization and connected-component sanity check, followed by a vertical refinement step that removes excess background.

D. MRZ-Adapted OCR

Recognition is a line-level sequence task: each extracted line is transcribed into a character string. No post-processing is applied—common confusions (e.g. $0/0$, $1/1$, $z/2$) are not corrected and missing fillers ($<$) are not inserted—so the raw recognizer output is evaluated.

The main recognizer is an SVTRv2-based CTC model from the PaddleOCR family. It supports supervised fine-tuning with a restricted output dictionary (digits 0–9, uppercase A–Z, and the filler $<$), matching the ICAO MRZ alphabet, and uses CTC decoding, which suits monotonic left-to-right MRZ lines [9, 10, 11]. Inputs are processed as colour images resized to 48×1024 pixels with aspect-ratio-preserving padding; the maximum text length is 44 characters (the longest TD3 line).

Training follows a multi-stage transfer-learning design (Fig. 2): starting from general pretrained PaddleOCR weights, the recognizer is (1) pretrained on a large synthetic MRZ corpus, (2) fine-tuned on public MRZ benchmark data, and (3) fine-tuned on the private target domain. All stages use AdamW; each stage initializes from the previous checkpoint.

Fig. 2. Multi-stage transfer-learning strategy for the SVTRv2 recognizer.

TABLE I

MRZ PORTION OF THE DATASETS USED. “UNIQUE DOCS” COUNTS DISTINCT MRZ IDENTITIES. TD1/TD3 COLUMNS COUNT MRZ SAMPLES PER ICAO FORMAT (NO TD2 DOCUMENTS ARE PRESENT IN THE PRIVATE SET; THE PUBLIC SETS CONTRIBUTE ALMOST EXCLUSIVELY TD3).

Dataset	Type	w/ MRZ	Uniq.	TD1	TD3
MIDV-500	public	4,500	14	0	4,200
MIDV-2020	public	28,949	400	0	28,949
MIDV-LAIT	public	680	180	0	680
Private	private	1,873	1,873	1,293	580
Syn-MRZ	synthetic	—	—	TD1/TD2/TD3	

The synthetic corpus (Syn-MRZ) was produced by a custom generator based on a published approach [12], extended to render isolated TD1/TD2/TD3 MRZ lines in OCR-B with character jitter, spacing variation, blur, bleed, rescaling, and JPEG compression.

Three OCR baselines are used for comparison: the generic open-source systems PP-OCRv3, PP-OCRv4, and PP-OCRv5 [13, 14, 15], applied out of the box, and the commercial service AWS Textract, also applied without MRZ-specific adaptation.

E. Datasets and Experimental Protocol

Experiments use the public MIDV-500, MIDV-2020, and MIDV-LAIT datasets [16, 17, 18] and a private target-domain dataset; an additional synthetic corpus is used only for OCR pretraining. These public datasets are among the few that contain realistic camera-captured identity-document data under challenging conditions. Only images that actually contain an MRZ are usable; in particular, front-side ID-card images in the public sets lack an MRZ and are excluded. Task-specific filtering was then applied (e.g. removing cut-off lines for OCR and removing documents with any cut-off line for the E2E task), and redundant near-duplicate video frames in MIDV-2020 were sub-sampled for OCR/E2E. Table I summarizes the MRZ portion of each dataset.

Three experimental setups were used consistently for detection, OCR, and E2E. *Experiment 1* trains on MIDV-500 and tests on MIDV-2020 and MIDV-LAIT; *Experiment 2* trains on MIDV-2020 and tests on MIDV-500 and MIDV-LAIT; *Experiment 3* trains and tests on the private dataset using a 70/15/15 document-level split. Because the public sets contain many captures of few unique documents, the public experiments were designed as cross-dataset evaluations to avoid optimistic results from near-duplicate leakage; for the private OCR split, all lines of one MRZ block were kept in the same partition. The private dataset is dominated by Swiss documents and reflects the intended deployment domain more closely than the public sets. All experiments ran on a single

workstation with one NVIDIA RTX 5090 GPU; no distributed or cloud compute was used.

F. Evaluation Metrics and Statistical Analysis

Detection is evaluated with mean pixel IoU (mIoU, threshold 0.5), object-based precision/recall/F1 using oriented-box IoU averaged over thresholds 0.50–0.80 following Ershova et al. [6], and the share of samples with per-sample CER < 50%, a coarse readability indicator from the recognition-quality protocol of Gayer et al. [2].

OCR and the E2E pipeline are evaluated with full-MRZ accuracy (the proportion of documents whose complete MRZ is recognized perfectly), line accuracy, CER, and the per-character recognition rate (PCR). With N lines, predicted/ground-truth lines p_i, g_i , Levenshtein distance $\text{lev}(\cdot, \cdot)$, and line length $|g_i|$,

$$\text{CER} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \text{lev}(p_i, g_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^N |g_i|}, \quad \text{PCR} = 1 - \frac{\sum_i \min(\text{lev}(p_i, g_i), |g_i|)}{\sum_i |g_i|}. \quad (1)$$

A character-recognition macro-F1 (treating recognition as multi-class classification over the alphabet, following Liu et al. [19]) is reported for comparison with prior work. Because all models were evaluated on the same samples, comparisons are paired; significance was assessed with two-sided paired Wilcoxon signed-rank tests, and p -values were corrected with the Benjamini–Hochberg procedure within each family of tests.

III. RESULTS

A. MRZ Detection

Table II reports detection performance. A clear separation appears between the lightweight HED-MRZ baseline and the three stronger models, which achieve consistently higher mIoU and object-F1. On the private set, HED-MRZ reaches only 56.35% mIoU and 37.83 object-F1, whereas DINOv3-L reaches 96.12% mIoU and 99.65 F1 (paired Wilcoxon with BH correction, $p < 0.0001$). No single model dominates every public transfer setting: U-Net is best in MIDV-500 → MIDV-2020, while DINOv3-L is best in MIDV-2020 → MIDV-500 and shows the strongest overall robustness under dataset shift. On the private domain, U-Net, DINOv2-S, and DINOv3-L all reach near-ceiling performance (mIoU > 95%, F1 > 99); the difference between DINOv3-L and U-Net was not significant ($p = 0.2572$). Qualitatively, model differences are largest under strong perspective distortion, where HED-MRZ frequently fails to localize the MRZ at all (Fig. 3).

Based on overall robustness—the best private-domain result, the highest mIoU in most public transfers, and low score dispersion—DINOv3-L was selected as the strongest detection model, with U-Net a very close alternative whose private-domain performance did not differ significantly.

B. MRZ OCR

OCR experiments used pre-cropped, geometrically rectified ground-truth line images, isolating recognition from detection. Table III shows that generic OCR systems do not

TABLE II
MRZ DETECTION PERFORMANCE (mIoU \pm STD AND OBJECT-BASED F1).
BEST mIoU PER BLOCK IN BOLD.

Test set	Model	mIoU (%)	F1
<i>Exp. 1 – train MIDV-500</i>			
MIDV-2020	HED-MRZ	55.59 \pm 29.99	68.97
MIDV-2020	U-Net	86.20 \pm 10.69	94.76
MIDV-2020	DINOv2-S	84.94 \pm 6.26	91.13
MIDV-2020	DINOv3-L	85.54 \pm 5.36	91.71
MIDV-LAIT	HED-MRZ	64.95 \pm 24.27	74.83
MIDV-LAIT	U-Net	85.17 \pm 9.59	92.78
MIDV-LAIT	DINOv2-S	84.95 \pm 9.08	92.15
MIDV-LAIT	DINOv3-L	85.25 \pm 8.59	92.86
<i>Exp. 2 – train MIDV-2020</i>			
MIDV-500	HED-MRZ	69.37 \pm 21.35	86.19
MIDV-500	U-Net	87.08 \pm 12.76	98.23
MIDV-500	DINOv2-S	86.94 \pm 11.84	97.90
MIDV-500	DINOv3-L	88.46 \pm 9.09	98.83
MIDV-LAIT	HED-MRZ	69.54 \pm 11.76	89.21
MIDV-LAIT	U-Net	83.07 \pm 8.89	93.66
MIDV-LAIT	DINOv2-S	83.26 \pm 8.40	95.01
MIDV-LAIT	DINOv3-L	85.19 \pm 8.17	94.61
<i>Exp. 3 – train/test private</i>			
Private	HED-MRZ	56.35 \pm 16.13	37.83
Private	U-Net	95.63 \pm 6.31	99.46
Private	DINOv2-S	95.59 \pm 3.68	99.49
Private	DINOv3-L	96.12 \pm 2.09	99.65

Fig. 3. Qualitative MRZ detection on two challenging MIDV-2020 samples, with the predicted region overlaid in green for HED-MRZ, U-Net, DINOv2-S, and DINOv3-L. HED-MRZ fails on both cases and U-Net and DINOv2-S recover only parts of the region, whereas DINOv3-L produces the most complete MRZ prediction. Differences between models are largest under strong perspective distortion.

transfer consistently to MRZ recognition and do not improve monotonically across PaddleOCR versions (PP-OCRv4 is frequently worse than PP-OCRv3 and PP-OCRv5). The synthetic-pretrained SVTRv2 recognizer is the strongest model across all baseline comparisons. The effect is largest on the private domain, where the best generic baseline (PP-OCRv5) reaches 73.80% line accuracy and 3.44% CER, while synthetic-pretrained SVTRv2 reaches 94.55% and 0.46% ($p < 0.0001$).

Fine-tuning on real MRZ crops improves performance further. In the public cross-dataset setting, real fine-tuning

TABLE III
OCR PERFORMANCE ON GROUND-TRUTH LINE CROPS. PER DATASET:
BEST GENERIC BASELINE, THE SYNTHETIC-PRETRAINED RECOGNIZER,
AND THE BEST FINE-TUNED RECOGNIZER. “FT” = FINE-TUNED ON THE
INDICATED SET. BEST VALUE PER BLOCK IN BOLD.

Test	Model	Full-MRZ (%)	Line (%)	CER (%)	PCR (%)
MIDV-500	PP-OCRv3 (best gen.)	52.84	61.66	9.55	90.45
MIDV-500	SVTRv2 (Syn-MRZ)	53.64	65.84	4.93	95.07
MIDV-500	SVTRv2 (MIDV-2020 ft)	66.06	76.81	1.57	98.43
MIDV-2020	PP-OCRv5 (best gen.)	45.89	54.27	12.48	87.52
MIDV-2020	SVTRv2 (Syn-MRZ)	59.77	65.69	6.54	93.46
MIDV-2020	SVTRv2 (MIDV-500 ft)	74.39	81.68	1.69	98.31
MIDV-LAIT	PP-OCRv5 (best gen.)	49.68	62.01	5.67	94.33
MIDV-LAIT	SVTRv2 (Syn-MRZ)	52.70	65.23	5.11	94.89
MIDV-LAIT	SVTRv2 (MIDV-500 ft)	66.03	76.13	1.52	98.48
Private	PP-OCRv5 (best gen.)	48.57	73.80	3.44	96.56
Private	SVTRv2 (Syn-MRZ)	91.43	94.55	0.46	99.54
Private	SVTRv2 (Private ft)	96.43	98.01	0.09	99.91

improves line accuracy by roughly 11–16 percentage points over the synthetic-only model (e.g. MIDV-500 \rightarrow MIDV-2020: 65.69% \rightarrow 81.68%; $p < 0.0001$). On the private domain, private fine-tuning raises performance to 98.01% line accuracy, 0.09% CER, and 96.43% full-MRZ accuracy ($p < 0.0001$).

a) *Error analysis*: The gap between PCR and exact line accuracy shows that most failures are partial rather than complete. Across the four cross-dataset MIDV evaluations, the recognizer was tested on 16,830 lines; of the 3,641 imperfect lines, 48.2% differed from the ground truth by a single character. Among near-perfect failures (edit distance ≤ 2), the most frequent substitutions were visually plausible glyph confusions under the monospaced OCR-B font: S \rightarrow 5 (171), M \rightarrow F (77), and X \rightarrow V (76). On the private domain, only 15 of 752 test lines were imperfect, with residual errors limited to rare letter–digit ambiguities (e.g. 0/O, 1/I, I/Z). These remaining errors are glyph-level ambiguities rather than failures to recover the MRZ structure. Figure 4 illustrates the qualitative pattern: in easy cases all systems are correct; under severe blur and low contrast all may fail, though SVTRv2 still preserves most of the MRZ; and in difficult but recoverable cases SVTRv2 stays exact while the generic baselines produce many substitutions or no usable output.

C. End-to-End Pipeline

The E2E results (Table IV) measure the full system from complete document images; the OCR checkpoint is fixed within each train/test configuration, and the variants differ only in the detection backbone. On the public transfers, no single backbone dominates: DINOv3-L is strongest in Experiment 1 on both targets, whereas in Experiment 2 U-Net achieves the best full-MRZ accuracy on MIDV-500 and the best complete result on MIDV-LAIT (86.77% full-MRZ). On the private domain, U-Net, DINOv2-S, and DINOv3-L are statistically indistinguishable and all reach near-ceiling performance, while HED-MRZ remains far behind (46.24% full-MRZ). Figure 5

conclusive.

IV. DISCUSSION

a) Principal findings: The pipeline answers the research question positively: on the private target domain the best E2E configuration reaches 96.42% full-MRZ accuracy, demonstrating that reliable MRZ extraction is possible without closed commercial OCR. Three sub-findings follow. First, the lightweight HED-MRZ baseline is clearly outperformed by U-Net, DINOv2-S, and DINOv3-L; DINOv3-L is strongest overall, but the three modern backbones are near-ceiling and statistically indistinguishable on the private domain. Second, generic OCR is insufficient: synthetic pretraining already improves over the strongest generic baselines, and fine-tuning on real MRZ crops reduces the error further, confirming that MRZ-specific adaptation is essential for exact line-level recognition. Third, high OCR accuracy on ground-truth crops does not directly translate to E2E performance, but the additional stages do not uniformly increase error; the per-document CER difference is small and bidirectional, and can even favour the pipeline because idealized line crops are sub-optimal under document bending. Overall, robust on-premise MRZ extraction requires a strong segmentation model, stable geometric processing, and an MRZ-adapted recognizer, rather than any single “best” detector.

b) Relation to prior work: The results are consistent with the observation that MRZ recognition from scans is largely solved while smartphone-based recognition remains challenging, and that recent research has focused on detection while OCR is often delegated to generic systems [2]. The large gap between the HED-MRZ-style re-implementation and the originally reported HED-MRZ result should be read cautiously: the baseline here was re-implemented from the paper description rather than from the original code or checkpoint, and the original method uses specific Hough blocks, bounded activations, reflection padding, many more training epochs, and dedicated post-processing [6]. The finding that newer generic OCR versions can be worse on MRZ text echoes earlier reports that general OCR improvements do not necessarily transfer to structured fields, supporting the view that MRZ recognition is a domain-specific OCR problem [25].

c) Limitations: The most important limitation is that the private dataset cannot be released, which limits external reproducibility. The dataset composition also constrains generality: it is dominated by Swiss documents and contains only TD1 and TD3 layouts, with TD2 absent from all datasets, and the public sets contribute almost exclusively TD3 passports—so three-line TD1 performance is effectively evaluated only on the private split. The public sets contain few unique documents, so cross-dataset results reflect document-level rather than independent-sample evidence. The pipeline still relies on heuristic rectification and an aspect-ratio line-splitting rule, which can truncate a line when the document is strongly curved. Finally, no post-processing was applied; many residual errors are isolated, visually plausible single-character substitutions, and a lightweight step that probes

common confusion substitutions and validates them against ICAO check digits could likely recover a measurable fraction of these cases.

d) Future work: Because recognition is the dominant remaining error source once a strong detector is used, future work should focus on recognition robustness, broader training and evaluation data (more document types, countries, and capture devices, and TD2 coverage), checksum-aware post-processing, and explicit measurement of deployment characteristics such as latency, memory, throughput, and cost—particularly relevant given that DINOv2-S matched DINOv3-L on the private domain with roughly $13\times$ fewer parameters.

e) Conclusion: A robust on-premise MRZ pipeline is feasible when MRZ detection is combined with an MRZ-adapted recognizer. On the private target domain the pipeline reached 96.42% full-MRZ accuracy and 98.33% line accuracy at a 0.07% character error rate, providing a transparent and controllable alternative to closed commercial OCR for privacy-sensitive identity-verification workflows.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Constantin Jann Eberdorfer conducted the research as part of the master’s thesis, including study conception, data collection, analysis, and drafting of the manuscript. The full master’s thesis is available from the library of the UAS Technikum Wien. Georg Brandmayr supervised the research process on a regular basis, provided conceptual guidance, critically reviewed the manuscript, and approved the final version for publication.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

This research was conducted in collaboration with an industrial partner that provided the private dataset and computing hardware, and the first author was affiliated with this partner during the work. The authors declare no other competing interests.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The public MIDV-500, MIDV-2020, and MIDV-LAIT datasets used in this study are available from their respective sources (see References). The synthetic MRZ data were produced with a custom generator based on a published approach [12]. The private target-domain dataset cannot be shared, as it contains personal identity-document data subject to data-protection constraints; only aggregate evaluation metrics are reported.

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